

IMPROVEMENT OF WAYS OF INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY OF METROLOGICAL SERVICE IN PRODUCTION

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Abstract. *In this article, ideas on improving the metrological service and ways of increasing its productivity in production and its branches are discussed. Information on metrological service and supply in production and its sectors is provided.*

Keywords: *production, metrological service, metrological supply, quality, demand.*

Introduction

The concept of metrological supply is very broad and includes technical measurements from increasing to ensuring the unity of measurements and regulatory metrology applied, mainly in the activity related to measurement, testing and control used and, in simultaneous production technological processes, the concept of metrological supply is also allowed to be used. Activities that form the organizational and methodological basis of metrological supply are the following:

1. Basics of metrological supply;
2. Regulatory and legal bases of metrology;
3. Metrological services and organizations.

Measurement information requires not only quantitative requirements but also qualitative ones. This includes attributes such as its accuracy, reliability, cost, and efficiency. All these quality attributes are based on metrological assurance.

Metrological assurance can be defined as:

- The establishment and implementation of technical means, procedures, rules, standards, scientific and organizational foundations necessary to ensure the unity of measurements and achieve the required accuracy.

Based on this description, the main tasks of metrological assurance include:

- Ensuring, providing, and implementing the serviceability of measuring instruments: This involves making sure that the measuring instruments are in good working order and meet the required standards.

- Developing and implementing normative documents for carrying out measurements, processing, and recommending the results: This ensures that all measurements are carried out according to a set of established procedures and that the results are interpreted and communicated accurately.

- Conducting document reviews: This involves evaluating the documentation related to measurements, ensuring its accuracy and completeness.

- Conducting state testing of measuring instruments: This ensures that measuring instruments meet the required standards and are fit for their intended purpose.

- Metrological certification and accreditation of measuring instruments and methods: This provides assurance of the quality and reliability of measuring instruments and methods used.

Literary analyses

To improve the effectiveness of metrological service in production, it is necessary to consider the following aspects:

1. Optimizing the organizational structure of metrological service:
 - Centralization: Centralizing metrological service in production allows for the concentration of qualified specialists in one place.
 - Interdepartmental collaboration: Strengthening collaboration between metrological service and production departments enables joint problem-solving and information exchange.
 - Automation: Automating metrological tasks reduces the likelihood of errors and increases productivity.
2. Implementing technological innovations:
 - Modern equipment: Introducing modern measuring instruments and equipment is essential to enhance the efficiency of metrological service.
 - Digital technologies: Implementing digital technologies facilitates data collection and analysis, as well as remote control and monitoring.
 - Standardization: Developing and adhering to standards and guidelines for the operation of metrological service helps to minimize errors and increase productivity.
3. Improving staff qualifications:
 - Continuous training: Establishing continuous training programs to enhance the qualifications of metrological service staff and familiarize them with new technologies is crucial.
 - Certification: Introducing a certification system to validate staff qualifications and enhance their professional level is necessary.
 - Motivation: Creating a motivation system to incentivize staff and improve their work efficiency is important.
4. Assessing and analyzing the effectiveness of metrological service:
 - KPIs: Developing a clear set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate the effectiveness of metrological service and regularly monitoring them is necessary.
 - Auditing: Regularly auditing the activities of metrological service and implementing corrective actions to address any shortcomings is important.
 - Error analysis: Analyzing errors occurring in metrological service and identifying their causes to prevent recurrence is essential.
5. Compliance with legislation and legal regulations:
 - Metrological legislation: Strict adherence to laws and regulations governing metrological service activities helps to prevent errors and ensure the quality of production.
 - Certification and accreditation: Compliance with certification and accreditation systems that validate the activities of metrological service ensures quality in production and compliance with international standards.

Implementing the above measures contributes to increasing the effectiveness of metrological service and ensuring quality and efficiency in production.

Component handling not only impacts the speed of the process, but also the accuracy of the results. When measuring complex parts, contact measurements may be necessary. A touch probe changer will allow a seamless transition between probe and styli types. This will avoid the need to manually change probes, which would interrupt the measurement routine and could result in movement of the part being measured, thus impacting on measurement results. When taking multiple automated measurements, the stability of the equipment is key. If components shift during

the measuring process, accuracy will be compromised. Ensuring the measuring equipment is stabilized with a heavy base, such as granite, provides the ideal solution. Choosing the right fixturing to hold components during measurement routines is also important.

Finally, efficiency of production will be compromised if the system and equipment used are so complex that it requires in-depth training and cross-checking. It may be the case that the same measurement process will need to be conducted by multiple operators. In these instances, it would be impractical to take the time to provide in-depth training to an entire team. Using software to automate these regular measurement procedures allows all team members to conduct the same tests with little or no training, without compromising on accuracy and speed. That said there may also be the requirement for more than one person to have the necessary skills to create an automated quality control process. Where this is an issue, it would be practical to select an intuitive, industry-standard software program. This may mean that the skillset already exists within the company, avoiding the need for any additional specialized training. Not all parts manufactured within a company need a routine measurement process. There may be instances where a small run of bespoke or prototype components need to be measured. If this is a consideration, it would be advantageous to use the same equipment as that used for automated processes. Our range of metrology systems are designed to match all of the options outlined here. Contact Vision Engineering to speak with a metrology specialist to determine which system is best suited for your application and production goals.

Conclusion

The level of metrological supply directly affects the quality of the product. In order to further increase the efficiency of this effect, special importance is given to metrological preventive works and issues of metrological maintenance in the preparation of production. This, in due course, will create a suitable basis for the deeper formation of market relations in our republic and the increase of the possibility of export of manufactured products.

Metrological supply is responsible for the following: organization, provision and implementation of the serviceability of measuring instruments; development and implementation of normative documents on carrying out measurements, processing and recommending its results; examination of documents; state tests of measuring instruments; metrological certification of measuring tools and methods, etc.

There are following organizations of metrological supply:

Scientific basis: metrology is the science of measurements;

Technical bases - state standards of units of magnitude, transfer of units from standards to working tools, creation and development of measuring tools, mandatory state tests of measuring tools and metrological attestation of methods of their execution in the development of measuring tools, conducting mandatory state comparisons in repair and use, creating standard samples for the composition and properties of substances and materials, standard references, product mandatory state tests.

The organizational basis is the metrological service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which consists of the metrological service of the state and courts.

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